

Improving Reproductive Performance of Laying Hens with a Combination of Selenium: Effects on FSH and LH Hormones

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to evaluate the provision of inorganic and organic selenium in feed on the reproductive status of layers. This research took the main object as layers aged 60 weeks with the ISA Brown strain. The research used a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method with Duncan's advanced test. The results of this study explain that giving additional feed in the form of selenium (Se) with several doses of basal feed plus inorganic selenium 1000 g/ton of feed and organic selenium 225 g/ton of feed showed a significant increase in the FSH hormone, while giving basal feed plus inorganic selenium at a dose of 2,500 g/ton of feed and organic selenium at a dose of 375 g/ton of feed gave a significant increase in the LH hormone. The best treatment results are because the additional feed contained in organic selenium can help layers improve reproduction to produce good quality eggs.

KEYWORDS: Feed additive, Inorganic selenium, ISA Brown strain, Layer, Organic selenium.

INTRODUCTION

The rising demand for eggs is intimately linked to adapting human habits, an increase in the need for animal protein produced from poultry products. Eggs are extensively consumed due to their low cost, accessibility, and high nutritional content. In response to this demand, layer farmers utilize aggressive production cycles to assure a consistent egg supply. However, various farm-level perspectives influence egg quality and productivity. Generally, there are two causes of egg production decrease: infectious and non-infectious. Mineral deficits in the diet are one of the most serious non-infectious causes. The availability of high-quality feed ingredients at affordable prices is a major challenge for farmers. Consequently, the high cost of commercial feed often drives farmers to formulate their own feed rations. These self-mixed rations, however, frequently lack balanced nutrition, which can result in variations in egg size and weight (Setiawati, 2016). Improving egg production requires the optimization of management practices, the use of nutritionally balanced feed, and the supplementation of essential vitamins and minerals. Nutrients such as proteins, vitamins, and minerals play a critical role in maintaining egg quality and enhancing the performance of laying hens. Minerals are required for cellular digestion and metabolism, as well as eggshell development. Selenium (Se) is an essential nutrient for laying chickens. Selenium is a component of glutathione peroxidase, an enzyme that eliminates free radicals in the cytoplasm. Selenium also serves as an antioxidant for enzyme components and materials, as well as for cattle immunity and reproduction. Vitamin E is a synergistic nutrient with selenium. There are two forms of selenium: organic and inorganic (Lubis *et al.*, 2015). The use of selenium in feed has both advantages and downsides. Selenium has several advantages, including strong antioxidants (Surai, 2002), high conception rates (Han *et al.*, 2017), stimulation of antibody development (Rayman, 2000), and improved egg quality. Meanwhile, selenium supplementation can pose dangers to layers, such as poisoning (Leeson and Summers, 2001), reduced bioavailability of inorganic selenium (Surai, 2006), and environmental damage when layers excrete selenium in feces (Nriagu, 1989). Selenium is found in a wide range of products on the market, including feed additives blended with feed or drinking water, as well as injection preparations. In several research studies, the widespread and routine use of selenium affects the reproductive and metabolic systems of laying hens, lowering egg quality and layer reproductive health. The reproductive health system is a unique concern in the layer; it is required that the reproductive organs operate well so that productivity achieves its peak. The anterior pituitary produces gonadotropin hormones, which include follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH). FSH hormone regulates the development of immature follicles into mature follicles. The follicles are forming oocytes, theca cells, and some granulosa cells. The production of nitric oxide in theca cells and granulosa cells can be inhibited by estrogen production. The secretion of steroids, namely estrogen and progesterone, by theca cells and granulosa cells is influenced by the FSH hormone, which plays an important

role in the formation of egg yolk, albumin, and eggshells. Gonadotropin hormones secreted by the anterior pituitary gland include follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH). LH promotes the maturation of ovarian follicles into preovulatory follicles, ultimately triggering ovulation (Hafizzudin *et al.*, 2012). Progesterone also plays a critical role in the development and functional regulation of the reproductive tract, particularly the oviduct, and is essential for the egg-laying process. Based on the introduction above, this study aims to evaluate and compare the effects of organic and inorganic selenium supplementation in layer diets on the productivity of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Materials

A. Layer

The layer chicken used 60 weeks with the ISA brown strain.

B. Materials

The study materials used are organic selenium with SELEN-OYE and inorganic Introvit E Selen-WS produced by Tekad Mandiri Citra company. Basic feed produced by PT. Malindo Feed Factory. Tbk, code 7605 with content on the feed label (protein min 16%, fiber max 7%, water max 7%, ash max 14%). Feed and drinking water are given in limited quantities.

C. Tools

The tools used are a battery cage (20 x 35 cm) complete with feeder and water, a 1 mL syringe, an EDTA tube, stationery, surgical scissors, gloves, and digital scales.

Research Methods

The research used the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method with Duncan's advanced test. There are four treatments and six repetitions, as explained here:

- P0 : Basic feed + organic selenium + inorganic selenium (150 g + 1000 g)/ton feed
- P1 : Basic feed + organic selenium + inorganic selenium (225 g + 1500 g)/ton feed
- P2 : Basic feed + organic selenium + inorganic selenium (300 g + 2000 g)/ton feed
- P3 : Basic feed + organic selenium + inorganic selenium (375 g + 2500 g)/ton feed

Data Analyst

The obtained research was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a test level of 5%. Data processing was done using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16.0 for Windows with a confidence level of 95%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

FSH Hormone

The research results showed that giving chicken layers a selenium combination (organic selenium and inorganic selenium) was significant (P<0.05) with the FSH hormone. The average of FSH hormone is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average of FSH Hormone

FSH Hormone (pg/mL)				
Component	P0	P1	P2	P3
Average ± SD	181.43 ± 3.169 ^d	294.34 ± 2.495 ^a	197.36 ± 1.527 ^c	279.51 ± 4.138 ^b

Note: ^{a, b, c, d} = Different superscripts in the same row indicate that the addition of selenium in the feed has a very significant effect (P<0.05) on FSH in layer eggs.

The results of the ANOVA statistical analysis above show significant differences between the four treatment groups. This study has a measurable effect on the outcome variables. The highest levels of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) were observed in Treatment 1, which involved a combination of inorganic selenium (1,500 g/ton of feed) and organic selenium (225 g/ton of feed) included in

the basal diet. Selenium plays a crucial role as a selenoprotein T synthesizer and regulates calcium homeostasis and neuroendocrine secretion. It can cause an increase in FSH levels. The anterior pituitary gland regulates FSH synthesis and secretion; selenoprotein T promotes hormone release by boosting the neuroendocrine signaling pathway.

The raw material for producing FSH hormone is fat or lipid; in general, the fat in the ration is digested in the small intestine with the help of bile salts into cholesterol, glycerol, and fatty acids, which are then distributed through the blood vessels, which later channel nutrients to the oviduct and help compose the yolk in the infundibulum, assisted by FSH (Sudaryani, 2003). The study findings show that variation in FSH hormone levels fluctuates in response to treatment. This is due to the gradual administration of organic and inorganic selenium. This study reported that selenium supplementation does not always cause an increase in FSH levels. This necessitates planning the volume of selenium dose administration because excessive amounts will result in overdoses and toxicities. Selenium overdose can induce primary symptoms such as hair loss and nail form abnormalities. Furthermore, earlier research has found multiple occurrences of layer chicken, such as skin lesions (redness, blisters) and nervous system abnormalities (paresthesia, paralysis, hemiplegia). FSH hormone is crucial in influencing the growth of young follicles into mature follicles. In addition, the FSH hormone has a role in the secretion of steroids, namely estrogen and progesterone, produced by theca cells and granulosa cells, which are important for the formation of egg yolk, albumen, and egg shells. This is an indicator of the reproductive status in livestock. The mechanism of FSH hormone formation begins with a glycoprotein, following Hadley's opinion (1992) that reproductive hormones are also called adrenal corticosteroid C-19 hormones. Primary androgens in the adrenals include dehydroepiandrosterone, androstenedione, and testosterone. Anabolic effects occur in the retention of N, P, K, Na, and Cl. In addition to steroid hormones, there are also gonadotropin hormones, whose working mechanisms are influenced by the hypothalamic-pituitary axis, structurally a group of glycoproteins, including TSH, LH, and FSH. This study shows that selenium can be converted into selenoprotein, which will later be related to the formation of glycoproteins that will affect FSH hormone levels.

LH Hormone

The research results showed that giving chicken layers a selenium combination (organic selenium and inorganic selenium) was significant ($P < 0.05$) with the LH hormone. The average of LH hormone is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Average of LH Hormone

LH Hormone (pg/mL)				
Component	P0	P1	P2	P3
Average ± SD	31.72 ± 1.023 ^c	39.99 ± 0.655 ^b	30.69 ± 4.873 ^d	54.03 ± 3.387 ^a

Note: ^{a, b, c, d} = Different superscripts in the same row indicate that the addition of selenium in the feed has a very significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on LH in layer eggs.

The results of the statistical analysis above show that the treatment gave a very significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the LH layer hormone levels. The average value of the LH layer hormone levels during the study, from the lowest to the highest in sequence, were P2 (30.69 ± 4.873), P0 (31.72 ± 1.023), P1 (39.99 ± 0.655), and P3 (54.03 ± 3.38) pg/ml. Several studies have reported the relationship between selenium status and the reproductive function of both male and female animals (Xiong *et al.* 2018).

Selenium deficiency in female livestock can cause pregnancy disorders such as pre-eclampsia, miscarriage, and premature birth (Rayman *et al.* 2014). The efficiency of mammalian reproductive organs depends on several factors, including genetics, nutrition, management, and environment. The status of micro minerals in feed is an important physiological factor for animal growth, development, and reproduction, including the health and performance of their reproductive organs (Xiong *et al.* 2018). The primary mechanism of selenium and vitamin E in reproductive diseases is their role as antioxidants, as indicated by their indirect involvement in prostaglandin synthesis, where peroxy radicals are a normal element of the metabolic mechanism (Surai *et al.* 2019). Similarly, vitamin E, an antioxidant, plays a direct role in fat metabolism and membrane cell integrity (Surai *et al.* 2019). The presence of microminerals in the body, such as copper, zinc, selenium, and molybdenum, can affect the animal reproductive system. These microminerals play a vital role in carbohydrate, protein, and fat metabolism; otherwise, the mechanisms that impact reproductive

organs are poorly known due to the complicated interactions between metallobiomolecules and neurohormones. Meanwhile, micro minerals in several organs, fluids, and reproductive tissues can provide information on the metabolism and role of these minerals (Siswanto *et al.* 2013; Kumar *et al.* 2011). Related to the role of selenium in the reproductive system, selenium can bind to the glutathione peroxidase enzyme in the body's defense system to release hydrogen peroxide (Rayman *et al.* 2014). Selenium enters the body through the interaction of seleno-P and W proteins, which are involved in thyroid hormone metabolism, testicular and sperm function, and muscle metabolism. As part of selenoproteins, selenium activity is structurally known for catalysis and antioxidants (Rayman *et al.* 2014). Selenoprotein plays a role in DNA deoxynucleotide synthesis, peroxide destruction, protein and membrane oxidation-reduction, redox signal regulators, thyroid hormone metabolism, and selenium transport and storage (Zhang *et al.* 2017).

Organic and inorganic selenium provide antioxidants in feed (Surai, 2002). They promote high fertility (Han *et al.*, 2017). They stimulate antibody proliferation (Rayman, 2000). They also improve egg quality (Skrivan *et al.*, 2010). Meanwhile, the provision of selenium can also pose a risk to layers, including toxicity (Leeson and Summers, 2001), having lower bioavailability in inorganic selenium (Surai, 2006), and harming the environment when layers excrete selenium in feces (Nriagu, 1989). The effects of administering selenium and vitamin E clinically and metabolically are the same; the function of protecting tissue membrane cells through the oxidation process is independent. The body requires selenium to produce GSH-Px, which eliminates harmful peroxides; however, vitamin E destroys the selenium protection. Selenium accumulates in the placenta, ovaries, pituitary gland, and adrenals, indicating a unique Se need in these tissues (Burk *et al.* 2013). Excess organic hydroperoxides in the cytosol cause cell membrane damage, which selenium and vitamin E protect against. These peroxides can react and damage cell membrane components through oxidation. Vitamin E reacts directly, while Se works as part of GSH-Px4. This enzyme catalyzes the following reactions: GSH-Px helps metabolize hydroperoxides (Ramos *et al.* 2015; Talukder *et al.* 2015). It supports the synthesis of various prostaglandin derivatives. It maintains the normal function of lymphocytes, neutrophils, and macrophages. It also preserves erythrocyte integrity. GSH-Px can also protect the sarcolemma and muscle fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

Researchers have reported that combining organic and inorganic selenium significantly affects FSH and LH hormone levels. This combination of laying hen feed offers both benefits and drawbacks for the birds' health and reproductive performance. Therefore, determining the optimal dosage is crucial to enhancing egg production while maintaining nutritional adequacy and overall feed quality.

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